

Enhancing the Affordability and Accessibility of Methylene Diphosphonate Radiopharmaceutical through Optimization in Low Resource Oncology Settings

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Purpose of Study: Methylene diphosphonate (MDP) radiolabeled with Technetium-99m (^{99m}Tc-MDP) is among the most widely used radiopharmaceuticals in oncology, primarily for the detection of skeletal metastases in patients with breast, prostate, and lung cancers. However, high costs, wastage of multidose kits, and dependency on cold-chain infrastructure hinder accessibility in low-resource oncology centers. This study assessed the stability and radiochemical purity (RCP) of fractionated MDP aliquots stored under ambient conditions, with the goal of establishing cost-effective strategies for sustainable nuclear oncology services.

Materials and Methods: A prospective experimental laboratory-based study design was applied at the University Teaching Adult Hospital Nuclear Medicine Hot Laboratory, Zambia. Forty MDP aliquots prepared from kit fractionation were stored at ambient (15–32 °C), refrigerated (2–8 °C), and frozen (–23 °C) conditions. Aliquots were labeled with ^{99m}Tc and tested for RCP using instant thin-layer chromatography. Data were analyzed with Stata 14.

Results: Ambient-stored MDP aliquots retained RCP values of 98–99% over 18 days, exceeding the WHO acceptance threshold of 90%. Refrigerated and frozen aliquots-maintained RCP values of 99–100% for 28 days. Statistical analysis using Pearson chi-square tests demonstrated significant differences in radiochemical purity with a *p* value of < 0.05.

Conclusion: In oncology practice, where bone scintigraphy is indispensable for staging and therapy monitoring, ambient storage of fractionated MDP offers substantial cost saving mechanisms and practical solution in low-resource settings. This method reduces radiopharmaceutical wastage, mitigates reliance on cold-chain logistics, and enhances access to essential cancer diagnostics.

Keywords: Technetium-99m, Methylene Diphosphonate, Radiochemical Purity, Bone Scintigraphy, Cancer Diagnosis, Radiopharmaceuticals

1.0 Introduction

Skeletal metastases are a major complication in advanced cancers, particularly in breast, prostate, and lung malignancies, often leading to pain, pathological fractures, and decreased quality of life (Coleman, 2006; Coleman et al., 2014). Early detection and monitoring of bone metastases are essential for staging and guiding therapy. Nuclear medicine plays a pivotal role in this domain, with Technetium-99m methylene diphosphonate (^{99m}Tc-MDP) bone scintigraphy remaining the gold standard imaging modality for skeletal metastases (Even-Sapir, 2005; Ibrahim et al., 2013; Cook and Fogelman, 2001).

MDP binds to hydroxyapatite crystals in bone, allowing for high-sensitivity detection of metastatic lesions and evaluation of treatment response (Schillaci et al., 2007; Okarvi, 2019). Despite its clinical utility, accessibility to MDP in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) is limited by cost, short half-lives, and reliance on cold-chain systems that are vulnerable to power outages (Zulu et al., 2024). Furthermore, in oncology centers with low patient volumes, multidose MDP kits often result in wastage when unused fractions expire (Vallabhajosula et al., 2011; Vallabhajosula et al., 2018).

Previous research demonstrates that fractionation and storage of radiopharmaceuticals under refrigerated or frozen an maintain radiochemical integrity for weeks to months (Bayomy et al., 2009; Bhatia et al., 2013). However, limited

evidence exists on the feasibility of ambient storage acknowledged as a gap in the scoping literature search, particularly in tropical regions. How does the Radiochemical Purity (RCP) of ambiently stored radiolabelled MDP fractions reconstituted with tin chloride augmented NS (NSSnCl_2) compare with those reconstituted with tin chloride augmented NS purged with argon (NSSnCl_2A)? This study investigated the possibility of using ambient-stored these MDP aliquots, highlighting implications for nuclear practice in resource-constrained settings. The preparation, storage, and use of radiopharmaceuticals in Zambia are guided by national regulatory frameworks, including oversight by the Zambia Radiation Protection Authority and adherence to international standards such as those of the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) and Good Manufacturing Practice (GMP) guidelines. These regulations emphasize strict quality control and cold-chain maintenance, which present practical challenges in resource-limited settings.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Preparation of Normal Saline Variants

A prospective experimental laboratory-based study conducted at the Nuclear Medicine Hot Laboratory of the University Teaching Hospital, Lusaka, Zambia.” The research was conducted according to the institutional and national research guidelines (Ethical approval No: NHRA0000015/01/06/2022).

Two packets of 500 mL normal saline (NS) were modified to produce two streams. The first (NSSnCl_2A) was argon-purged with stannous chloride added, while the second (NSSnCl_2) had only stannous chloride added. For the preparation of argon-purged normal saline (NSSnCl_2A), medical-grade argon gas was introduced into 500 mL normal saline using a sterile needle system at an approximate flow rate of 1–2 L/min for 15 minutes to displace dissolved oxygen. The container was partially vented using a second sterile needle to allow gas escape and prevent pressure build-up. Immediately after purging, stannous chloride was aseptically added, and the container was sealed to minimize reintroduction of oxygen.

2.2 MDP Aliquot Preparation

A total of 40 aliquots were prepared, with 20 aliquots per saline stream. For each stream, 18 aliquots were stored under ambient conditions (16–32 °C) for 18 days, while 2 aliquots were stored under refrigerated conditions (2–8 °C) and 2 aliquots under frozen conditions (–23 °C) for 28 days to serve as reference controls. An MDP vial was diluted with 4 mL of the respective saline streams. One mL was then withdrawn from each vial and dispensed into sterile vials, yielding 40 aliquots. Eighteen aliquots per stream were stored at ambient conditions (16–32 °C) for 18 days, two refrigerated (2–8 °C), and one frozen (–23 °C) for 28 days.

2.3 Radiochemical Purity (RCP) Testing

Aliquots were labeled with $^{99\text{m}}\text{Tc}$ and tested using instant thin-layer chromatography with saline and methyl ethyl ketone as mobile phases. Radiochemical purity (RCP) was determined using instant thin-layer chromatography (ITLC-SG) following established protocols for $^{99\text{m}}\text{Tc}$ -labelled radiopharmaceuticals (16, 17). Normal saline (0.9% NaCl) was used as the mobile phase to quantify hydrolyzed-reduced technetium ($^{99\text{m}}\text{TcO}_2$), while methyl ethyl ketone (MEK) was used to quantify free pertechnetate ($^{99\text{m}}\text{TcO}_4^-$), in accordance with standard methods (e.g., United States Pharmacopeia and International Atomic Energy Agency technical guidelines) RCP was calculated based on free pertechnetate ($^{99\text{m}}\text{TcO}_4^-$), hydrolyzed colloid ($^{99\text{m}}\text{TcO}_2$), and labeled compound. IAEA and WHO standards require $\geq 90\%$ RCP for clinical use (Jones, 2021).

2.4 Data Analysis

Data were entered and analysed using Stata version 14 (StataCorp, College Station, TX, USA). Radiochemical purity (RCP) values were expressed as means \pm standard deviation (SD). Normality of the data distribution was assessed using the Shapiro–Wilk test. For comparison of mean RCP values between the two preparation streams (NSSnCl_2 vs NSSnCl_2A), an independent samples t-test was applied for normally distributed data, while the Mann–Whitney U test was used for non-parametric data. Comparisons across multiple storage conditions (ambient, refrigerated, and frozen) were performed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) for normally distributed data, followed by Tukey’s post hoc test, or the Kruskal–Wallis test with Dunn’s post hoc correction for non-parametric data. Categorical comparisons of RCP compliance with WHO thresholds ($\geq 90\%$) were analysed using the Chi-square test or Fisher’s exact test where appropriate. A p-value of < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

3.0 Results

The MDP was reconstituted as indicated by the manufacturers and then subjected to different storage temperatures and time period. As indicated in Table 1, the RCP for all streams of aliquots ranged from 98 to 100%. The Radiochemical Purity which was our dependant variable showed a reduction of 1 or 2 percent from the one stored at recommended conditions. The reduction, however, remained within the WHO accepted threshold of $\geq 90\%$ RCP.

Table 1: RCP of All Streams Of MDP

Aliquot Age (Days)	Radiochemical purity (%)	Radiochemical purity (%)	Radiochemical purity (%)	Radiochemical purity (%)
	NS	NSSnCl ₂	NSSnCl ₂ A	NSA
1	99	99	99	99
2	99	99	99	98
3	99	100	100	99
4	99	99	99	99
5	99	100	100	99
6	99	100	100	99
7	99	100	100	99
8	99	100	100	99
9	99	100	100	99
10	99	100	100	98
11	99	100	100	98
12	99	100	100	100
13	99	98	98	99
14	99	99	99	99
15	99	100	99	98
16	99	99	99	100
17	99	99	99	99
18	99	98	99	99

Statistical analysis using Pearson chi-square (Tables 2 and 3) tests demonstrated significant differences in radiochemical purity between selected preparation methods ($p < 0.05$). This can be attributed to presence of a reducing agent stannous chloride.

Table 2: Pearson Chi-square results for MDP aliquots from NSSnCl₂ and NSSnCl₂A

		NSSnCl ₂ A				
NSSnCl ₂						Total
	0.98	1 7.6	1 0.0	0 0.9	0 0.1	2 8.7
	0.99	0 0.3	6 4.8	0 2.8	0 0.3	6 8.3
	1.00	0 0.5	1 2.4	9 3.8	0 0.5	10 7.3
	NSSnCl ₂	0 0.1	0 0.4	0 0.5	1 17.1	1 18.0
	Total	1 8.5	8 7.7	9 8.1	1 18.0	19 42.3
		Pearson chi ² (9) = 42.2750			Pr = 0.000	

The P-value in Table 2 was 0.000 which indicated that there is a significant difference between MDP aliquots reconstituted with non-Argon purged NS and Stannous Chloride versus those reconstituted with Argon purged NS and Stannous Chloride, and that the observed difference in the Radiochemical Purity results from the two aliquots were not by chance.

Table 3: Pearson Chi-square results for (MDP) aliquots reconstituted with Argon purged Normal Saline (NSA) versus those reconstituted with non-Argon purged NS.

		Argon purged Normal Saline Aliquot (NSA)				
Normal Saline (NS) RCP (%)						Total
	0.98	3 0.1	9 0.3	0 1.3	0 0.6	12 2.3
	0.99	1 0.0	3 0.0	1 0.4	0 0.3	5 0.7
	1.00	0 0.2	0 0.6	1 7.6	0 0.1	1 8.5
	NS RCP	0 0.2	0 0.6	0 0.1	1 17.1	1 18.0
	Total	4 0.5	12 1.5	2 9.4	1 18.0	19 29.4
		Pearson χ^2 (9) = 29.4500		Pr = 0.001		

The P-value in Table 3 was 0.001 which indicated that there is a significant difference between aliquots of NSA and aliquots reconstituted with NS, and that the observed difference in the RCP results from the two aliquots was not by chance.

The comparison of RCP of aliquots made from NSSnCl_2 and NSSnCl_2A stream compared to those kept at recommended conditions is shown in Figures 1 and 2. The RCP findings comparison between the NSSnCl_2 stream fractions kept at and the fractions kept at recommended (frozen and refrigerated) conditions shown in the image below. The NSSnCl_2 stream is represented by the colour green, whereas the frozen stream is represented by colour blue and the refrigerated stream is represented by the colour red.

Figure 1: Average Radio-Chemical Purity (RCP) of aliquots prepared from non-Argon purged Normal Saline and Stannous Chloride (NSSnCl_2) kept at ambient compared to those kept recommended conditions (frozen & refrigerated once-off). Series 1 represents aliquots kept at below 0°C (-23°C), series 2 represents aliquots kept at 2 to 8°C (3°C) and series 3 represents aliquots kept ambient conditions (25°C to 42°C).

The RCP findings comparison between the NSSnCl_2A stream fractions kept at and the fractions kept at recommended (frozen and refrigerated) conditions shown in the image below. The NSSnCl_2A stream is represented by the colour green, whereas the frozen stream is represented by colour blue and the refrigerated stream is represented by the colour red.

Figure 2: Average Radio-Chemical Purity (RCP) of aliquots made from Argon purged Normal Saline and Stannous Chloride (NSSCL₂A) kept at ambient compared to those kept at recommended conditions (frozen & refrigerated once-off). Series 1 represents aliquots kept at below 0°C (-23°C), series 2 represents aliquots kept at 2 to 8°C (3°C) and series 3 represents aliquots kept ambient conditions (27°C).

4.0 Discussion

This study evaluated the feasibility of storing fractionated methylene diphosphonate (MDP) radiopharmaceutical aliquots under ambient conditions as a strategy to improve access and reduce wastage in low-resource oncology settings. The findings demonstrate that MDP aliquots maintained radiochemical purity (RCP) values of 98–99% for up to 18 days under ambient conditions (16–32 °C), remaining well above the WHO-recommended threshold of ≥90% for clinical use. Aliquots stored under recommended refrigerated and frozen conditions showed slightly higher RCP values (99–100%) over 28 days, consistent with expected stability profiles.

These results confirm that ambient storage of fractionated MDP is a technically viable alternative to conventional cold-chain-dependent storage, particularly in settings where infrastructure limitations and inconsistent power supply present major operational challenges. The marginal differences in RCP between ambient and recommended storage conditions were not clinically significant, suggesting that ambient storage does not compromise radiopharmaceutical quality within the evaluated timeframe. This has important implications for improving the reliability and continuity of nuclear medicine services in resource-constrained environments.

From a health systems perspective, the adoption of ambient storage strategies offers substantial cost and operational advantages. Fractionation of multidose MDP kits reduces wastage, particularly in centers with low patient throughput, while minimizing reliance on refrigeration and freezing infrastructure. This directly translates into improved cost-efficiency and sustainability of nuclear medicine services, aligning with broader efforts to enhance equitable access to cancer diagnostics in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) (Fleming et al., 1992). Additionally, reducing dependency on cold-chain logistics enhances service resilience in the face of frequent power interruptions, a common challenge in many LMIC settings.

The findings of this study are consistent with previous investigations on radiopharmaceutical fractionation under controlled storage conditions. Thokchom et al., 2022 reported that fractionated ^{99m}Tc-MDP stored at –20 °C maintained RCP values above 95%, although a decline was observed after several days depending on the storage method (Thokchom et al., 2022). Similarly, studies by J. Zulu et al. 2024; demonstrated reductions in RCP to 83.6% and 88% by day eight under certain conditions (Zulu and Mudenda, 2024; Zulu and Sakala, 2024), highlighting the influence of preparation and storage techniques on radiochemical stability. In addition to physicochemical assessment, biodistribution and image quality were evaluated in 100 patients, demonstrating appropriate localization of the radiotracer in target tissues and confirming clinical usability.

Dhingra et al. evaluated the stability of multiple radiopharmaceutical kits, including MDP, DMSA, and DTPA, reporting average RCP values of 95%, 91%, and 95%, respectively, following refrigerated storage at -20 to -30 °C for up to 15 days (Dhingra and Dhingra, 2019). Similarly, Bayomy et al. demonstrated that fractionated MDP aliquots stored under frozen (-20 to -28 °C) and refrigerated (0 – 4 °C) conditions maintained high RCP values (98.56% and 97.15%, respectively) over 30 days, with successful biodistribution observed in human subjects (Bayomy et al., 2009).

While these studies primarily focused on refrigerated and frozen storage, the present study extends existing knowledge by demonstrating that ambient storage under tropical conditions can also maintain acceptable RCP levels, thereby offering a practical and context-appropriate alternative for LMIC settings.

Despite these promising findings, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the number of aliquots stored under recommended conditions ($n = 2$ each for refrigerated and frozen) was limited, which may restrict the statistical robustness of comparisons between storage conditions. Second, the study was conducted as a laboratory-based investigation without direct patient-based biodistribution or imaging data, limiting the ability to fully assess clinical performance beyond radiochemical purity. Third, the single-site study design may affect the generalizability of findings to other settings with different environmental conditions, handling practices, or regulatory frameworks. Additionally, longer-term stability beyond 18 days for ambient conditions was not evaluated and warrants further investigation.

Notwithstanding these limitations, the study provides important practical insights for nuclear medicine practice in resource-constrained environments. Bone scintigraphy using ^{99m}Tc -MDP remains essential for cancer diagnosis, staging, and treatment monitoring, particularly in breast, prostate, and lung cancers (Vallabhajosula et al., 2018; Chopra, 2009). Ensuring consistent availability of MDP through cost-effective and logistically feasible approaches can significantly enhance diagnostic capacity. The use of fractionation combined with ambient storage reduces wastage and supports more efficient utilization of limited radiopharmaceutical resources (Zulu and Mudenda, 2024; Zulu and Sakala, 2024), while also strengthening service continuity in the absence of reliable cold-chain systems.

5.0 Limitations and Recommendations

5.1 Limitations

Limited sample size for control conditions: The number of aliquots stored under recommended conditions (refrigerated and frozen) was small ($n = 2$ per condition per stream), which limits the statistical power and robustness of comparisons across storage conditions.

Absence of patient-based clinical validation: The study was purely laboratory-based and did not include biodistribution or imaging data in patients, restricting conclusions to radiochemical purity without direct confirmation of *in vivo* clinical performance.

Single-site study design: The study was conducted at one laboratory site, which may limit the generalizability of findings to other settings with different environmental conditions, handling practices, or infrastructure constraints.

5.2 Recommendations

Conduct multi-centre validation studies: Future research should include multi-site studies across different climatic and operational settings to improve the generalizability of findings and confirm the feasibility of ambient storage under varying real-world conditions.

Increase sample size for control conditions: Studies should incorporate a larger number of aliquots under refrigerated and frozen conditions to strengthen statistical comparisons and enhance the reliability of conclusions.

Undertake patient-based clinical evaluations: Further investigations should include biodistribution studies and imaging in patients to confirm that ambient-stored MDP aliquots maintain not only radiochemical purity but also clinical diagnostic performance and safety.

Evaluate longer-term stability under ambient conditions: Additional studies should explore extended storage durations beyond 18 days to determine the maximum safe and effective shelf-life under ambient conditions.

Standardize preparation and storage protocols: Development of standard operating procedures (SOPs) for fractionation, argon purging, and ambient storage is recommended to ensure reproducibility and facilitate regulatory acceptance.

Engage regulatory bodies for guideline development: Collaboration with national and international regulatory authorities (e.g., radiation protection agencies, IAEA) is essential to integrate ambient storage strategies into formal guidelines and policy frameworks.

6.0 Conclusion

This study demonstrates that fractionated methylene diphosphonate (MDP) aliquots can be stored under ambient conditions (25 – 35 °C) for up to 18 days without compromising radiochemical purity, maintaining values within the WHO-accepted threshold for clinical use. These findings highlight a practical, safe, and cost-effective alternative to conventional cold-chain-dependent storage, particularly relevant for low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) where infrastructure limitations and radiopharmaceutical wastage remain significant challenges.

The adoption of fractionation combined with ambient storage has the potential to reduce operational costs, minimize wastage of multidose kits, and improve the reliability and accessibility of nuclear medicine services, thereby strengthening equitable access to essential cancer diagnostics.

Future research should focus on multi-centre validation, larger sample sizes, extended stability beyond 18 days, and patient-based clinical evaluations, including biodistribution and imaging outcomes. Additionally, cost-effectiveness analyses and the development of standardized protocols will be essential to support regulatory acceptance and facilitate

the integration of this approach into routine nuclear medicine practice.

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